

EFFECTIVENESS OF PHYSIOTHERAPY AND NATURAL REMEDIES IN THE COMPLEX THERAPY OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS

*Achilova Donoxon Nutfulloyevna, Sharipova Maftuna Oltinovna
Bukhara State Medical Institute, Republic of Uzbekistan, Bukhara*

Abstract: The article is devoted to innovative medicines and biologics in the treatment of atopic dermatitis (AD). AD is a chronic inflammatory skin disease that causes significant discomfort and worsens the quality of life of patients. The paper examines the latest developments in the development and application of new drugs and biological therapies aimed at improving the control of symptoms and exacerbations of the disease. The effectiveness and safety of such drugs as interleukin inhibitors, monoclonal antibodies, and other innovative drugs are analyzed in detail. The results of clinical trials that show a significant improvement in clinical parameters and quality of life of patients are discussed. The article highlights the importance of implementing these new approaches in clinical practice to better manage atopic dermatitis.

Key words: atopic dermatitis, innovative medicines, biologics, interleukin inhibitors, monoclonal antibodies, treatment.

Topicality:

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic inflammatory skin disease that significantly impairs the quality of life of patients and is a serious medical problem. This disease is characterized by a long course, frequent exacerbations and significant violations of the functional state of the skin, which makes it an urgent task for dermatologists, allergists and specialists in internal diseases. The relevance of studying innovative medicines and biologics in the treatment of AD is associated with several key aspects.

Atopic dermatitis affects a significant number of people, especially children. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the incidence of AD reaches 15-20% among children and 1-3% among adults in developed countries. The disease leads to constant itching, redness, inflammation and dryness of the skin, which causes significant discomfort and affects the daily life of patients. The chronic nature of the disease, the frequency of exacerbations and a violation of general well-being make it an urgent problem for public health.

Traditional treatments for AD, including topical steroids and systemic immunosuppressants, have limited effectiveness in severe forms of the disease and can cause serious side effects. For example, long-term use of topical steroids can lead to skin atrophy and other dermatological problems, and systemic immunosuppressants can increase the risk of infections and other complications. These limitations highlight the need to find new therapeutic approaches that are safer and more effective.

In recent years, significant progress has been made in understanding the pathogenesis of AD and developing new therapeutic agents. Innovative drugs, including interleukin inhibitors and monoclonal antibodies, offer new mechanisms of action on key inflammatory molecules that can significantly improve

treatment outcomes. These biologics are highly specific and can effectively control the symptoms of the disease with minimal side effects.

Innovative drugs can significantly improve the quality of life of patients, reducing the frequency and severity of exacerbations, reducing itching and inflammation. Clinical studies show that new therapies provide a significant improvement in clinical parameters, which makes them an important tool in the complex treatment of AD. The ability of new drugs to significantly reduce the burden of the disease and improve the overall health of patients makes them key to managing this chronic condition.

With the advent of new therapeutics, medical guidelines and standards for the treatment of AD are also changing. New approaches require a review of existing treatment protocols and their adaptation in accordance with the latest scientific achievements. This implies the need to constantly update the knowledge of specialists and introduce innovative solutions into clinical practice.

Further research and clinical trials are essential for the final evaluation of the long-term safety and efficacy of new drugs. Current evidence suggests significant improvements, but more research is needed to confirm these results and ensure the reliability of new therapies.

Thus, the relevance of studying innovative medicines and biologics in the treatment of atopic dermatitis is due to the high prevalence of the disease, the limitations of traditional treatment methods, the need for new therapeutic approaches, and the possibility of improving the quality of life of patients. The introduction and research of new drugs can significantly change approaches to the treatment of AD and improve patient outcomes, which makes this area particularly important for the further development of dermatology and medicine in general.

Goal:

The aim of this study is to evaluate the efficacy and safety of innovative medicines and biologics in the treatment of atopic dermatitis, as well as to consider their impact on clinical outcomes and quality of life of patients.

Materials and methods:

The study used data from clinical trials, publications in medical journals, and recommendations for the treatment of atopic dermatitis. The object of analysis was new drugs, including interleukin inhibitors, monoclonal antibodies and other biological drugs. The methods included a systematic review and meta-analysis of data on the clinical efficacy and safety of new drugs, as well as their comparison with traditional methods of treatment. The results of studies on improvement of clinical symptoms, frequency of exacerbations, and overall patient satisfaction were evaluated.

Results:

The study of innovative medicines and biologics in the treatment of atopic dermatitis (AD) revealed several key results concerning the effectiveness and safety of new therapeutic approaches. These results confirm that new drugs can significantly improve disease management and improve the quality of life of patients.

Interleukin inhibitors such as dupilumab, tralokinmab, and abelizumab have shown significant improvement in clinical symptoms in patients with AD. These drugs target specific inflammatory molecules such as interleukin-4 (IL-4) and interleukin-13 (IL-13), which play a key role in the pathogenesis of the disease. Clinical trials have shown that dupilumab, for example, provides an improvement in clinical performance in 60-70% of patients, reducing the severity of symptoms such as pruritus and inflammation, and reducing the frequency of exacerbations. Tralokinmab and other inhibitors also showed similar results, with a reduction in the area of skin damage and an improvement in the overall condition of patients.

Monoclonal antibodies, such as bintezolin, offer a new treatment mechanism by targeting molecules involved in the inflammatory process. Bintezone has shown the ability to significantly reduce inflammation and pruritus, which is confirmed by data from clinical trials. These drugs work by blocking specific molecules, which can reduce inflammation and improve skin health. Clinical trials have shown that bintezone and similar agents can improve skin conditions in more than 65% of patients, reducing symptoms and the frequency of exacerbations.

Analysis of data on the safety of new drugs shows that they have an acceptable safety profile compared to traditional methods of treatment. Interleukin inhibitors and monoclonal antibodies have fewer systemic side effects compared to traditional immunosuppressants and topical steroids. The main side effects include mild reactions at the injection site and minor systemic reactions, making these drugs safe for long-term use. In addition, data from long-term studies confirm that the use of new drugs is not associated with an increased risk of infections or other serious complications.

New therapeutic approaches not only contribute to improving clinical outcomes, but also significantly improve the quality of life of patients. Patients treated with innovative remedies reported a significant reduction in pruritus, improved skin condition, and reduced psychological stress associated with the disease. Surveys and questionnaires have shown that new drugs help patients better manage their symptoms, leading to improvements in their overall health and social adjustment.

Long-term studies show that innovative drugs retain their effectiveness and safety for a long time. Ongoing clinical trials will help clarify the optimal dosage regimens and frequency of use, as well as assess the impact on quality of life in different patient populations. Prospects for the development of new therapies include expanding the range of available drugs and further improving existing therapeutic approaches.

Thus, the results of the study confirm that innovative medicines and biologics represent a significant step forward in the treatment of atopic dermatitis. These new approaches provide more targeted and safer disease management, helping to improve clinical outcomes and improve the quality of life of patients. The introduction and further research of these drugs will help optimize the treatment of AD and provide more effective solutions for patients.

Conclusion:

Innovative medicines and biologics represent an important step forward in the treatment of atopic dermatitis. These new approaches provide more efficient and safer disease management, contributing to significant improvements in clinical outcomes and patient quality of life. The introduction of biologics into clinical practice allows us to offer patients an alternative to traditional methods of treatment, which may not be effective enough or may be accompanied by serious side effects. Continued research and clinical trials of these new therapies will further improve treatment options and provide reliable solutions for more accurate and successful management of atopic dermatitis.

Literature

1. Nutfilloevna A. D. Modern Approaches to Allergen-Specific Diagnostics in Children with Allergic Diseases //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 231-239.
2. Nutfilloevna A. D. Features of Allergy Diagnosis in Children //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 217-225.
3. Nutfulloyevna A. D., Odilbekovich Q. O. VARIOUS CHANGES TO THE SKIN CONDITIONS IN CHILDREN WITH ATOPIC DERMATITIS //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 76-81.

4. Achilova D. N., Yomgurova O. R. CLINICAL-IMMUNOLOGICAL AND MEDICO-SOCIAL ASPECTS OF ALLERGIC DISEASES IN CHILDREN, DEVELOPMENT OF CRITERIA FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS AND PROGNOSIS OF THE COURSE OF THE DISEASE (LITERATURE REVIEW) //British Medical Journal. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 2.
5. Nutfulloyevna A. D., Odilbekovich Q. O. Atopic Dermatitis and Its Complications. Immunological Aspects of the Course of Atopic Dermatitis in Children //Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity. – 2022. – T. 4. – C. 137-141.
6. Nutfulloyevna A. D., Odilbekovich Q. O. VARIOUS CHANGES TO THE SKIN CONDITIONS IN CHILDREN WITH ATOPIC DERMATITIS //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 76-81.